

NOTES

A Note on the Cohesive Surface Force at Oil-Water Interface

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It is generally believed that at oil-water (o/w) interface cohesive force of the van der Waals type between the CH₂ groups of the neighbouring long chain ions does not exist. In some recent publications, Ghosh^{1,2} suggested that in the case of long chain ions, the cohesive force of the van der Waals type exists at o/w interface at low substrate concentration. In the present communication, some evidence available in the literature³ has been cited in support of Ghosh's view.

On the basis of electrostatic repulsion and interionic attraction, Ghosh¹ proposed, for the surface pressure, π , of long chain electrolytes at o/w interface an equation which is of the following form:

$$\pi = \frac{2kT}{A_0} \ln \left(\frac{A}{A-A_0} \right) + (\exp^{(A-A_0)a/A} - 1) \frac{kT}{A_0} \ln \left(\frac{A}{A-A_0} \right) - \frac{5.8\sqrt{C_i}}{1+0.7\sqrt{C_i}} \quad (1)$$

where A is the film area per long chain ion, A_0 the limiting area, C_i the substrate concentration, and the other terms have their usual significance. The equation (1) is applicable to sparingly soluble long chain electrolytes as also to insoluble long chain electrolyte spread as monolayers at o/w interface.

The following equation of Davies⁴ has also been used for a comparative study:—

$$\pi = \frac{kT}{A-A_0} + 6.1\sqrt{C_i} \left[\text{Cosh sinh}^{-1} \left(\frac{134}{A\sqrt{C_i}} \right) - 1 \right] \quad (2)$$

where $(A\sqrt{C_i}) < 38$, equation (2) reduces to

$$\pi = \frac{3kT}{A-A_0} - 6.1\sqrt{C_i} - \frac{2kT A_0}{A(A-A_0)} \quad \dots (3)$$

Equations (1), (2) and (3) have been subjected to test using the data on spread films of HO(CH₂)₁₆COO⁻ at a substrate concentration of 1.0 (*M*) sodium hydroxide at oil/water interface as reported by Davies³.

From the considerations of van der Waals theory of attraction, Chatteraj and Chatterjee⁵ have proposed the following equation for cohesive surface pressure, π_s :

$$\pi_s = \frac{\alpha_s}{A^2} \quad \dots (4)$$

1. B. N. Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **45**, 1120.
2. B. N. Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **47**, 557.
3. J. T. Davies, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1953, **49**, 949.

where α_S is a constant for a given thickness of the interface. Both Davies⁴ and Chatteraj⁵ have pointed out that below $A = 110\text{\AA}^2$, deviation from the aforesaid equations becomes perceptible. In this paper, π_S has been calculated from equation (4). The difference between the observed and the calculated values of surface pressure is plotted against A^{-2} , the straight line that fits the plot best is drawn and α_S is evaluated from its slope.

TABLE

Film area A (in \AA^2)	Values of π observed ³ for films of $\text{HO}(\text{CH}_2)_{16}\text{COO}^-$ at a substrate conc. of $1.0(M)$ NaOH (in dynes cm^{-1})	π_a	π_g	$(\pi_g - \pi_S)$
		Calculated ⁴ [$A_0 = 30\text{\AA}^2$] (in dynes cm^{-1})	Calculated ¹ [$A_0 = 41\text{\AA}^2$] (in dynes cm^{-1})	Calculated ^{1,5} [$\alpha_S = 1.3 \times 10^4$] (in dynes cm^{-1})
200	3.7	3.3	3.6	3.3
150	4.6	5.4	6.0	5.4
100	9.4	10.9	10.8	9.5
80	12.6	13.9	14.8	12.8

From the data recorded in the table, it has been found that for the values of $A = 150$ to 80\AA^2 , the observed values of π are lower than the calculated values at a substrate concentration of $1.0(M)$. This may be attributed to the fact that the combined pull of two polar groups attached to the long chain ion, $\text{HO}(\text{CH}_2)_{16}\text{COO}^-$, at its two ends is strong enough to drag some of the CH_2 groups into the aqueous part of the interface and there they attract similarly situated CH_2 groups of the neighbouring molecules and give rise to cohesive force. The values of $(\pi_g - \pi_S)$ agree well with the observed values of π at a substrate concentration of $1.0(M)$ NaOH.

Hence, it may be concluded that with long chain ions cohesive force at o/w interface exists even at a substrate concentration of $1.0M$.

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4. J. T. Davies and E. K. Rideal, *Interfacial Phenomena*, Acad. Press, N.Y., 1961, p. 230.
5. A. K. Chatterjee and D. K. Chatteraj, *J. Coll. and Interface Sci.*, 1966, **21**, 159.